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3 **Heat stress affects some physiological and productive variables and alters metabolism in**
4 **dairy ewes**

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9
10 **ABSTRACT**

11 Heat stress (HS) has a significant economic impact on the global dairy industry.
12 However, the mechanisms by which HS negatively affects metabolism and milk synthesis in
13 dairy ewes are not well defined. This study evaluated the production and metabolic variables in
14 dairy ewes under controlled HS conditions. Eight Lacaune ewes (75.5 ± 3.2 kg body weight; 165
15 ± 4 days of lactation; 2.31 ± 0.04 kg milk per day) were submitted to thermo-neutral (TN) or HS
16 conditions in a crossover design (2 periods, 21 d each, 6 d transition). Conditions (day-night, 12-
17 12 h; relative humidity; temperature-humidity index, THI) were: TN ($20 - 15^{\circ}\text{C}$; $50 \pm 5\%$; THI =
18 $65 - 59$) and HS ($35 - 28^{\circ}\text{C}$; $45 \pm 5\%$; THI = $83 - 75$). Ewes were fed ad libitum and milked
19 twice daily. Rectal temperature (RT), respiratory rate (RR), feed intake, water consumption, and
20 milk yield were daily recorded. Milk and blood samples were collected weekly. Additionally, TN
21 and HS ewes were exposed to glucose tolerance test, insulin tolerance test, and epinephrine
22 challenge. Heat stress reduced feed intake (-11%), and increased RT ($+0.77^{\circ}\text{C}$), RR ($+90$

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23 breaths/min) and water consumption (+28%). Despite the reduced feed intake, HS ewes
24 produced similar milk to TN ewes, but their milk contained lower fat (-1.7 points) and protein (-
25 0.86 points). Further, HS milk tended to contain more somatic cells (+0.23 log points). Blood
26 creatinine was greater in HS compared to TN, but no differences in blood glucose, non-esterified
27 fatty acids or urea were detected. When glucose was infused, TN and HS had similar insulin
28 response, but higher glucose response (+85%) was detected in HS ewes. Epinephrine infusion
29 resulted in lower non-esterified fatty acids response (-215%) in HS than TN ewes. Overall, HS
30 decreased feed intake, but milk production was not affected. Heat stress caused metabolic
31 adaptations that included increased body muscle degradation and reduced adipose tissue
32 mobilization. These adaptations allowed ewes to spare glucose and to avoid reductions in milk
33 yield.

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35 **Key words:** milk production, metabolism, heat stress, dairy ewes

36

37 INTRODUCTION

38

39 Sheep production is one of the most important agricultural activities in the Mediterranean
40 area and several regions in the world. The European Mediterranean countries account for more
41 than 13% of the world sheep population, and 28% of the global dairy sheep production is
42 concentrated in this region (FAOSTAT, 2018). Sheep milk is mainly used for cheese production,
43 and alterations in milk yield or milk quality will impact cheese yield. Predictions relative to
44 climate change effects consider the Mediterranean basin as one of the regions where larger
45 increases in temperatures are expected (Pasqui and Di Giuseppe, 2019).

46 The sheep thermo-neutral zone is claimed to be between 5 and 25°C (Curtis, 1983).
47 Another study on the relationship between production traits and climatic variables indicated a
48 comfort zone between 11 and 21°C of average daily temperature (Ramon et al., 2016). Heat
49 stress (**HS**) negatively affects milk yield and its components in Holstein dairy cows (Baumgard
50 et al., 2011) and Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (Salama et al., 2014). With regard to dairy
51 sheep, most of the available studies evaluated the impact of HS on milk production by comparing
52 between seasons (Finocchiaro et al., 2005; Peana et al., 2007; Ramon et al., 2016). These studies
53 detected reductions in milk yield and milk components during summer. However, in studies
54 comparing seasons, the effect of HS was often confounded with that of different feeding patterns
55 across seasons. To the best of our knowledge, no published studies have evaluated the detailed
56 responses of lactating dairy ewes to HS under controlled climatic and feeding conditions.

57 With regard to metabolism under HS, available results in dairy cows (Wheelock et al.,
58 2010; Baumgard et al., 2011) and goats (Hamzaoui et al., 2013; Salama et al., 2014; Mehaba et
59 al., 2019) indicated homeorhetic adaptations to suppress lipid mobilization, despite reduced feed
60 intake and increased maintenance requirements. Studies comparing between heat-stressed and
61 thermo-neutral pair-fed cows showed that the lack of body lipid mobilization induced by HS is
62 because of greater blood insulin accompanied by changes in the expression of gluconeogenic
63 genes in liver (Wheelock et al., 2010; Baumgard et al., 2011). Furthermore, heat-stressed dairy
64 cows (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2013) and goats (Salama et al., 2014; Mehaba et al. 2019)
65 experience increased protein catabolism, and some of these mobilized AA could be used for
66 glucose synthesis. Whether similar metabolic changes occur in heat-stressed lactating dairy ewes
67 is not known.

68 The identification of HS animals and understanding the physiological mechanisms by
69 which HS reduces milk production is critical for developing novel approaches to minimize
70 production losses during HS conditions. Furthermore, little attention has been paid to evaluate
71 comprehensively the productive and metabolic responses to HS in lactating dairy ewes.
72 Therefore, the objectives of the present study were to evaluate the impact of HS on productive
73 variables (milk yield and milk composition) and to measure the metabolic and physiological
74 responses of dairy ewes to HS under controlled climatic chamber conditions.

75

76

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals, Treatments, and Management Conditions

78 Animal care conditions and management practices were approved by the Ethical
79 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
80 (Ref. 3142), following procedures described in the Spanish and EU legislations (R.D. 53/2013,
81 and Council Directive 2010/63/EU).

82 Eight multiparous lactating Lacaune dairy ewes (75.5 ± 3.2 kg BW; 165 ± 4 DIM; $2.31 \pm$
83 0.04 L/d of milk yield) with healthy and symmetrical udders were used. Animals were allocated
84 individually in 1.62 m²-pens (1.8×0.90 m) with separate feed and water throughout the
85 experiment. Ewes were blocked in two balanced groups according to milk yield and milk
86 composition. The experimental design was a crossover with two periods of 21 days each, and
87 two climatic treatments that differed in the temperature-humidity index (**THI**) values. With the
88 aim to have the same wool length in all animals, ewes were shorn before the beginning of the
89 experiment to have 2-cm long fleece.

90 Ewes were adapted to the experimental conditions for 14 d. Afterwards, ewe groups were
91 randomly assigned to 2 treatments: thermo-neutral conditions (TN; 15 to 20 °C, 50 ± 5% relative
92 humidity, THI = 59 to 65) or HS (12-h day at 35°C day and 45 ± 5% relative humidity; THI =
93 83; and 12-h night at 28°C and 45 ± 5% relative humidity; THI = 75). After the first period, 6 d
94 of transition was allowed, during which all ewes remained at TN conditions. Ewes were switched
95 to the opposite treatment in the second period. Photoperiod was 12-h light (0800 to 2000 h):12-h
96 dark (2000 to 0800 h). The THI were calculated according to NRC (1971).

97 Throughout the experiment (February to May), the ambient temperature of TN ewes was
98 maintained at 15 to 20°C with the help of an electric heater equipped with a thermostat (3.5
99 kW; General Electric, Barcelona, Spain) when needed. The HS ewes were kept in a 4 × 6 × 2.3-
100 m climatic chamber as described by Hamzaoui et al (2013). Ewes were machine-milked twice
101 daily (0800 and 1700 h). All TN and HS ewes were individually fed ad libitum a TMR (Table 1)
102 once daily (0900 h) and orts were recorded daily. The diet was formulated to meet or exceed the
103 predicted requirements (INRA, 2018) of energy, protein, minerals, and vitamins. Clean water
104 was permanently available at ambient temperature.

105 *Sampling, Measurements and Analyses*

106 Rectal temperature (**RT**) and respiratory rate (**RR**) were registered 3 times daily (0800,
107 1200, and 1700 h). The RR was determined by counting flank movements for 12s and
108 multiplying by 5. The RT was measured using a digital thermometer (Accu-vet, ST714AC,
109 Tecnovet S.L, Barcelona, Spain; reading range 32.0 to 42.0°C and accuracy ± 0.10°C).

110 Feed intake and water consumption was measured daily throughout the experiment. Feed
111 samples were collected before the beginning of each experimental period and were analyzed for

112 DM, ADF, NDF, CP and ash contents according to AOAC (2003). The chemical composition
113 and nutritive value of ration ingredients are shown in Table 1.

114 Ewes were weighed weekly using an electronic scale (Tru-test A6500, Auckland, New
115 Zealand) in 2 consecutive days after milking and before feeding. The net energy balance was
116 calculated using the following equation: energy balance = net energy intake – (NE_M + NE_L). The
117 NE_M was calculated using the following equation: NE_M = (0.0345 × BW^{0.75}; INRA, 2018).
118 Maintenance costs were increased by 30% for HS ewes as recommended (NRC, 2001). The NE_L
119 was calculated by using the following equation: NE_L = [0.2224 + 0.0071 (fat, g/kg) + 0.0043 ×
120 (protein, g/kg)] × 0.686 × milk yield (INRA, 2018).

121 Milk yield at each milking was weighed by electronic scale (Mobba industrial, Barcelona,
122 Spain) and registered daily. Milk samples at each milking were collected twice per week. Milk
123 samples were analyzed for fat, protein (N × 6.38), lactose, and SCC as previously described
124 (Mehaba et al., 2019). A milk aliquot was stored at –20°C to determine milk osmolality using a
125 Fiske 110 osmometer (Fiske Associations, Norwood, MA).

126 Two 10-mL blood samples were collected at 0800 h (before milking and feeding) from
127 the jugular vein using heparinized and K₂-EDTA vacutainer tubes (BD, Belliver Industrial
128 Estate, Plymouth, UK) at d 3, 10 and 17 of each period. Plasma was obtained by centrifugation at
129 2,000 × g for 15 min at 4°C and stored at –20°C until the analyses of glucose, non-esterified fatty
130 acids (NEFA), BHB, cholesterol, and albumin (Mehaba et al., 2019). Additional blood samples
131 (approximately 0.3 mL) were collected and immediately applied to disposable cartridges (i-
132 STAT CHEM8+; Abbott Point of Care Inc., Princeton, NJ). Then, the cartridge was inserted into
133 an i-STAT hand-held analyzer, and the results of glucose, BUN, creatinine, hematocrit,
134 hemoglobin, Cl, Na, K, Ca ions, total CO₂ concentration, and anion gap were obtained.

135 On d 15 of the second period, each ewe was fitted with indwelling jugular silicone rubber
136 catheters (Nutricath Silicone, 60 cm length and 14-gauge, Vygon, Valencia, Spain). On d 17, 19,
137 and 21 glucose tolerance test (**GTT**; 0.25 g/kg BW), insulin tolerance test (4.6 μ g/kg BW), and
138 epinephrine challenge (2 μ g/kg BW) were done, respectively. Dextrose (D9434, Sigma-Aldrich,
139 St-Louis, Missouri), insulin (bovine insulin form pancreas, I6634, Sigma-Aldrich) and
140 epinephrine (E4250, Sigma-Aldrich) were diluted in sterile 0.9% NaCl solution (Vitulia 0.9%,
141 Laboratorios ERN S.A., Barcelona, Spain). All solutions were sterilized by filtration through
142 0.22 μ m polyether-sulfone filters (Millex-GP, Millipore; Merck Life Science S.L.U., Madrid,
143 Spain) using 1 filter for each 200 mL solution and kept at 4°C.

144 On the day of each metabolic test, 3 pre-challenge blood samples (-20, -10, 0 min) were
145 collected followed by an intravenous bolus dose of the corresponding metabolite. Thereafter,
146 blood samples were collected at 5, 10, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90, and 120 min. After each blood
147 sampling, the catheters were flushed with heparinized 0.9% saline solution (500 IU/mL; Clexane
148 4000 UI, Sanofi Aventis, Paris, France). Plasma was harvested by centrifugation for 15 min at
149 $2,000 \times g$ at 4°C and stored at -20 °C for further analysis. Plasma insulin concentration was
150 analyzed by ELISA immunoassay sandwich type for quantitative determination of ovine insulin
151 in plasma (Mercodia, Diagnostics, Uppsala, Sweden). Glucose was analyzed by the hexokinase
152 method (OSR 6121, Reagent System Olympus, Beckman Coulter, Krefeld, Ireland). Values of
153 NEFA and BHB were determined as indicated by Mehaba et al. (2019).

154 Area under the curve (**AUC**) of metabolite responses to GTT, insulin tolerance test and
155 epinephrine challenge was calculated by the trapezoidal method after the correction for the
156 baseline values. Plasma baseline data were obtained by averaging the corresponding values at
157 min -20, -10 and 0. Values of peaks or nadirs of each metabolite after infusions were recorded.

158 Glucose clearance rate and glucose half-life during the GTT were calculated according to
159 Kerestes et al. (2009). For insulin tolerance test, insulin-stimulated blood glucose response was
160 calculated as indicated by Kerestes et al. (2009).

161

162 *Statistical Analyses*

163 Data were analyzed by the MIXED procedure for repeated measurements of SAS v. 9.4
164 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC). The statistical mixed model contained the effects of
165 environmental conditions (TN and HS), period (1 and 2), the sampling time, and the
166 environmental conditions \times period, environmental conditions \times sampling time, period \times
167 sampling time interactions as fixed effects, as well as the random effects of the animal and the
168 residual error. For the data of RT and RR measured at 0900, 1200 and 1700 h, a fixed factor of
169 the hour of day was added to the model. Data of performances (i.e., DMI, water consumption,
170 and milk yield) and physiological indicators (i.e., RT and RR) were analyzed on a weekly basis.
171 For the basal levels of physiological challenge parameters a t-test for independent means were
172 used. Differences between least squares means were determined with the PDIFF option of SAS.

173

174 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

175

176 *Rectal Temperature and Respiratory Rate*

177 The RT was greater (+ 77°C on average; $P < 0.001$) in HS than TN ewes (Table 2).
178 Furthermore, RT increased ($P < 0.05$) in HS ewes from 39.38°C at 0800 to 39.85°C at 1700 in
179 accordance with increment in the ambient temperature from 28°C during night to 35°C during the
180 day. However, RT did not vary between 0800 and 1700 h in TN ewes. Heat-stressed ewes had
181 214% increase in RR (+90 breaths/min; $P < 0.001$) on average compared with that for TN ewes.

182 The HS ewes increased ($P < 0.05$) RR by 34% in the evening (154 breaths/min) compared with
183 that for the morning measurement values (115 breaths/min). The increased RR in HS ewes was
184 to dissipate heat, as ~65 % of body heat is lost through the respiratory tract in sheep under
185 hyperthermia (Hales and Brown, 1974). Our ewes were shorn before the experiment (2-cm fleece
186 length), and some heat dissipation by sweating could have also occurred in addition to
187 evaporation by panting.

188

189 ***Feed intake and Body Weight Change***

190 The DMI decreased ($P < 0.001$) in HS ewes by 11% throughout the experiment (Table 2).
191 This lower DMI induced slight negative energy balance in HS compared to TN ewes (Table 2).
192 Reduction in appetite under HS is a primarily result of the elevated body temperature. The
193 reduced DMI may be also related to an increase in gut fill as a result of an increase in water
194 consumption (Silanikove, 1992). The rumen seems to serve as a water reservoir during high heat
195 load (Silanikove, 1992). The decrease in DMI observed in our HS ewes is lower than those
196 values reported in Holstein dairy cows (-30%; Wheelock et al., 2010) and Murciano-Granadina
197 goats (-21%; Hamzaoui et al., 2013) heat-stressed to similar extent as in the present study. In
198 addition, our HS ewes did not experience significant milk yield losses (see later). Consequently,
199 it seems that dairy ewes experience less productive losses under HS conditions compared to
200 dairy cows and goats. This assumption should be confirmed by carrying out comparative studies
201 using animals from the different species at similar stage of lactation and feeding conditions. The
202 HS ewes had greater water consumption compared with TN ewes (+2.0 L/d; $P < 0.001$).
203 Obviously, the increase in water consumption in the present study was mainly to meet the
204 increment of water requirements for heat dissipation by evaporation.

205 The HS ewes lost BW, whereas TN ewes gained weight (Table 2; $P < 0.01$). On average,
206 HS ewes lost 18 g/d, whereas TN ewes gained 214 g/d. This loss in BW in HS ewes agrees with
207 the slight negative energy balance detected compared with that for TN ewes (Table 2). Under HS
208 conditions, maintenance requirements increase because of the increment in energy expended for
209 heat dissipation and the production of high amounts of heat shock proteins. In addition, HS
210 Holstein cows (Ronchi et al., 1999) and Murciano-Granadina goats (Salama et al., 2014)
211 mobilize muscles and use some AA for gluconeogenesis. Our HS ewes also degraded muscles as
212 indicated by greater blood creatinine levels compared with that for TN ewes (see later).

213

214 ***Milk yield and Milk Composition***

215 Despite the reduced DMI and increased RT and RR, HS ewes produced similar milk
216 yield and FCM compared with that for TN ewes (Table 2). Our ewes were in their second half of
217 lactation, and milk yield response to HS would have been different if ewes were in earlier stage
218 of lactation. Abdalla et al. (1993) also reported that crossbred (Finn \times Dorset \times Rambouillet)
219 early lactating ewes do not suffer milk yield losses under controlled HS conditions (constant
220 35°C, 55% relative humidity, THI = 86). Additionally, Hamzaoui et al. (2013) under controlled
221 climatic conditions observed that HS Murciano-Granadina goats in late lactation produce similar
222 milk yield to TN goats. Nevertheless, in the studies evaluating the effect of HS by comparing
223 among seasons, milk yield of mid-lactating Sarda ewes was reduced by 15% when maximum
224 ambient temperature is higher than 24°C (Peano et al., 2007). Further, late-lactating Comisana
225 ewes experience a reduction in milk yield at temperatures $> 35^\circ\text{C}$ (Sevi et al., 2001). Evaluating
226 the impact of HS by the comparison between seasons includes the inevitable variations related to
227 different feeding and photoperiod conditions, and these variations were not present in our study.

228 Compared to TN, HS decreased milk fat and protein contents by 13 to 16 %, respectively
229 (Table 2). Similarly, Abdalla et al. (1993) reported that milk fat and protein contents are
230 depressed by HS in crossbred ewes. In addition, Ramon et al. (2016) reported a reduction in fat
231 and protein yields during summer in Manchega ewes. In the present study, lactose content was
232 increased in HS ewes compared with that for TN ($P < 0.05$) in accordance with the numerical
233 increment in milk yield. Despite the reduced fat and protein contents by HS, fat, protein, and
234 lactose yields were not affected (Table 2), which might be caused by the numerical increment in
235 milk yield by HS. Consequently, the mammary synthetic capacity was not impaired by HS in our
236 ewes, which is in contrast to what recently observed in bovine mammary cells (Salama et al.,
237 2019).

238 Heat stress tended to increase ($P < 0.10$) milk SCC by 5% in HS ewes compared with
239 that for TN ewes. It is not clear why milk SCC increased by HS, but stressful conditions such as
240 sudden change in milking regimen (Salama et al., 2003) and social isolation (Stelwagen et al.,
241 2000) result in increased milk SCC. The \log_{10} of SCC values in our TN and HS ewes (4.40 to
242 4.63) are well below the reported thresholds of mammary inflammation in sheep (5.48 to 6.00;
243 Murphy et al., 2018). This indicates that the increment of milk SCC in HS ewes is unlikely
244 related to mammary inflammation. In contrast to our results, Caroprese et al. (2011) reported no
245 change in milk SCC in ewes exposed to solar radiation compared to ewes maintained in shade.

246 Milk osmolality increased ($P < 0.001$) by HS (Table 2). Nevertheless, a decreased milk
247 osmolality was observed in heat-stressed goats (Olsson and Dahlborn, 1989) and Friesland ewes
248 (Thompson et al., 1981), which is related to over-hydration and hemodilution. Milk osmolality is
249 under strict control, and is isotonic with plasma. Lactose is the major osmotic component of
250 milk, and the increase in milk lactose content in HS ewes might explain the small (+1%), albeit

251 significant, increment in milk osmolality. In the current study, values of milk osmolality (298 to
252 302 mOsm/kg) were close to the normal osmolality reported for sheep milk (294 mOsm/kg;
253 Thompson et al., 1981). Additionally, the treatment \times period interaction was significant, which
254 indicates inconsistent response of milk osmolality to HS throughout periods. All together makes
255 the detected significant difference in milk osmolality caused by HS marginally relevant.

256

257 ***Blood Metabolites***

258 There were no differences between treatments in blood electrolytes (Table 3).
259 Nevertheless, HS ewes tended ($P < 0.10$) to have increased blood Cl concentration compared
260 with that for TN ewes. Usually, high ambient temperatures result in a reduction in blood Na, K,
261 Ca and P, and an increase in Cl concentrations (Hamzaoui et al., 2013; Mehaba et al., 2019).
262 Similar to our results, HS had no effect on blood Na and K concentrations in late lactating
263 Murciano-Granadina goats, but Cl levels increased (Hamzaoui et al., 2013). Blood total CO₂
264 concentration dropped ($P < 0.05$) by HS as a result of panting and greater removal of blood CO₂.

265 No differences were observed between TN and HS ewes with regard to blood glucose,
266 cholesterol, NEFA, or BHB values (Table 3). Similarly, heat-stressed late lactating Murciano-
267 Granadina dairy goats (Hamzaoui et al., 2013) and early-lactating crossbred ewes (Abdalla et al.,
268 1993) are able to keep similar blood glucose levels to TN animals. Possible explanations of how
269 HS ewes were able to keep blood glucose values are discussed hereafter. The lack of a NEFA
270 response to HS despite the negative energy balance was also reported in Murciano-Granadina
271 dairy goats (Hamzaoui et al., 2013; Mehaba et al., 2019) and Holstein dairy cows (Baumgard et
272 al., 2011). Nevertheless, Abdalla et al. (1993) detected increased blood NEFA levels in early
273 lactating crossbred ewes exposed to 35°C compared to control ewes at 20°C. Hemoglobin and

274 hematocrit values did not vary between TN and HS ewes. Similarly, packed cell volume and
275 hemoglobin were unaffected in HS Murciano-Granadina goats (Hamzaoui et al., 2013), although
276 some studies showed increases (Okoruwa, 2014) or decreases (Singh et al., 2016) in HS sheep.
277 Discrepancy among studies could be explained by differences in the specie, breed, aptitude
278 (dairy vs. non-dairy), stage of lactation, and heat stress intensity and duration.

279 Values of BUN and albumin were not affected by HS (Table 3). However, there was an
280 increase ($P < 0.001$) in blood creatinine in HS ewes compared with that for TN ewes, which
281 might indicate muscle degradation. Although our HS dairy ewes experienced lower DMI and had
282 slightly negative energy balance (Table 2), they did not use body fat reserves (no change in
283 blood NEFA as shown in Table 3). However, they mobilized body protein presumably to use
284 some glucogenic AA for glucose synthesis. Heat-stressed Murciano-Grnadina dairy goats also
285 experience increased blood creatinine levels compared to TN animals (Mehaba et al., 2019).

286

287 ***Responses to the Metabolic Tests***

288 ***Glucose Tolerance Test.*** Results of the GTT as indicator of insulin sensitivity are shown
289 in Figure 1 and Table 4. The basal glucose levels were not different in TN and HS ewes. Glucose
290 peaked at 5 min in both treatments, but the peak was greater ($P < 0.05$) in HS (+511%) than in
291 TN (+252%) ewes (Figure 1a). Blood glucose levels gradually decreased in both treatments and
292 returned to the basal values by 60 min after glucose administration.

293 Basal plasma insulin values did not differ between TN and HS ewes (Figure 1b; Table 4),
294 although DMI was depressed by HS. Maintaining blood insulin levels during HS is crucial for
295 the activation of the cellular stress response (Li et al., 2006). Further, insulin is a potent lipogenic
296 and antilipolytic hormone (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2013). Consequently, maintaining normal

297 insulin levels during HS might explain the absence of significant differences in blood NEFA
298 concentrations between TN and HS ewes (Table 2). As a response to the glucose infusion,
299 plasma insulin levels of both TN and HS ewes peaked at min 10, but no differences in peak
300 values were observed between groups. After the peak, insulin values decreased gradually and
301 reached the basal levels at min 90. The HS ewes had greater ($P < 0.05$) insulin values than TN
302 ewes only at 5 and 20 min (Figure 1b).

303 Mean glucose AUC tended ($P < 10$) to be greater at 45 and 90 min in HS ewes compared
304 with that for TN ewes (Table 4). However, the insulin AUC values did not differ between
305 groups. Wheelock et al. (2010) also found that lactating HS cows have greater glucose response
306 after GTT than TN cows fed ad libitum without differences in the insulin response. With similar
307 insulin secretion kinetics during GTT, HS ewes had greater immediate glucose level than TN
308 ewes, which might be interpreted as decreased insulin sensitivity in HS ewes. This greater
309 available glucose in HS ewes was rapidly uptaken, resulting in increased ($P < 0.01$) glucose
310 clearance rate and decreased ($P < 0.01$) glucose half-life (Table 4). Glucose is the most
311 efficiently utilized energy source compared to other substrates as fat or protein (Baldwin et al.,
312 1980), which might explain its fast disappearance in HS conditions. Because of the apparent lack
313 of NEFA availability as a fuel substrate, it seems that heat-stressed animals increase both their
314 production of, and reliance on, glucose as a fuel. As insulin response to GTT did not vary
315 between TN and HS ewes (Table 4), the faster uptake of glucose in HS ewes might have been
316 caused not only by insulin, but also through a non-insulin-mediated glucose uptake process. In
317 fact, the whole body utilization of glucose can also occur through noninsulin-dependent
318 pathways in crossbred wethers (Janes et al., 1985) and Holstein cows (Rose et al., 1997).

319 ***Insulin Tolerance Test.*** Results of the insulin tolerance test as indicator of insulin
320 responsiveness are shown in Figure 2 and Table 4. Plasma glucose concentration in both groups
321 decreased to a nadir at 30 min post-infusion. Thereafter, blood glucose values elevated, and by
322 120 min they returned to the basal values in HS ewes, but not in TN (60.9 ± 3.5 vs. 50.9 ± 3.4
323 mg/dL for TN and HS ewes, respectively; $P < 0.05$). This result indicates prolonged effect of
324 insulin in TN compared to HS ewes (Figure 2).

325 However, taking all time points into consideration, insulin AUC and insulin-stimulated
326 blood glucose response did not vary between TN and HS ewes (Table 4), which might be
327 interpreted as unchanged insulin responsiveness. This result agrees with the findings of Achmadi
328 et al. (1993) who found that glucose amount needed to keep euglycemia when insulin is infused
329 do not vary between TN and HS Suffolk ewes. Given the fact that blood glucose did not return to
330 the basal levels by min 120 in TN ewes (Figure 2), it is possible that differences in insulin
331 responsiveness kinetics would have been detected if sampling time was extended beyond 120
332 min. Neither plasma NEFA nor BHB concentrations were affected by the insulin infusion,
333 although NEFA AUC was lower in HS compared with that for TN ewes (Table 4). The lower
334 NEFA AUC levels in HS ewes might be related to the increased dependence on glucose as
335 energy source and the decreased body fat mobilization.

336 ***Epinephrine Challenge.*** Plasma glucose peak in response to the epinephrine challenge
337 was similar between groups (Table 4), but HS ewes had an earlier peak (5 min) than TN ewes
338 (10 min) as shown in Figure 3a. At 10 min, TN ewes had greater ($P < 0.05$) blood glucose (114
339 mg/dL) than HS ewes (99 mg/dL). Similar glucose AUC between TN and HS ewes suggests
340 equal liver sensitivity to epinephrine with regard to breaking down glycogen and releasing
341 glucose.

342 Blood NEFA levels (Figure 3b) were lower in HS ewes than TN ewes from 30 min after
343 infusion until min 120. The blunted lipolytic response to epinephrine in HS ewes occurred
344 despite the reduced DMI, which is typically associated with elevated circulating NEFA levels.
345 Baumgard et al. (2011) also demonstrated that HS Holstein cows have reduced NEFA response
346 to epinephrine administration. Epinephrine has been reported to be elevated during HS,
347 especially during the early phase (acute) of hyperthermia (Silanikove et al., 2000). This elevation
348 could modify the density and affinity of the adrenergic receptors (Mirit et al., 2000), which could
349 explain the increased resistance of adipose tissue to lipolytic signals in HS ewes.

350 Alternatively, the released NEFA in HS ewes were rapidly uptaken by liver and
351 converted into ketone bodies. This would explain the greater ($P < 0.05$) AUC of BHB (Table 4)
352 in HS compared with that for TN ewes. Salama et al. (2014) proposed that liver of HS Murciano-
353 Granadina goats is able to uptake NEFA faster and converts them to BHB (utilized as energy
354 source for body tissues to spare glucose) compared to TN goats.

355

356 CONCLUSIONS

357 Heat stress reduced feed intake, but Lacaune dairy ewes were able to maintain milk yield
358 as well as the yields of fat, protein and lactose. Heat-stressed ewes did not mobilize body fat
359 reserves, but degraded muscles as indicated by the greater blood creatinine levels. Heat-stressed
360 ewes tended to have more available glucose in the blood after glucose was administered, and it is
361 likely that this glucose was uptaken through insulin- and noninsulin-mediated pathways. Further,
362 adipose tissue of HS ewes became more resistant to the lipolytic signals. Overall, these metabolic
363 adaptations allowed dairy ewes to spare glucose and to avoid reductions in milk yield.

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468 **Table 1.** Ingredients, chemical composition, and nutritive value of the total mixed ration offered
 469 to the dairy ewes.

Item	Value
Ingredients (% as fed)	
Alfalfa hay	60.0
Cracked oat grain	2.0
Cracked corn grain	1.6
Brewing barley	4.0
Soybean hull	18.0
Soybean meal, 44%	2.0
Rapeseed meal	4.0
Corn gluten feed	4.0
Soybean oil	2.0
Cane molasses	0.8
Salt (NaCl)	0.2
Vitamin and mineral complex for goats	0.4
Dicalcium phosphate	1.0
Chemical composition (% of DM)	
Dry matter	87.9
Organic Matter	87.8
Crude protein	17.0
Ether extract	3.73
Neutral detergent fiber	26.5
Acid detergent fiber	17.6
Acid detergent lignin	3.02
Nutritive value ¹	
UFL ² , /kg	0.92
NEL ³ , Mcal/kg	1.62
PDI ⁴ , g/kg	91.2
PDIA ⁵ , g/kg	42.8
RPB ⁶ , g/kg	34.3
Ca _{abs} , g/kg	3.04
P _{abs} , g/kg	5.38

470 ¹ Calculated according to Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA, 2018).

471 ² Feed units for lactation.

472 ³ Net energy for lactation (1 UFL = 1.7 Mcal of NE_l).

473 ⁴ Protein digested in the small intestine from food and microbial synthesis origins.

474 ⁵ Protein digested in the small intestine supplied by food rumen undegradable protein.

475 ⁶ Rumen protein balance, represents RUP, microbial protein and endogenous protein.

476 **Table 2.** Rectal temperature, respiratory rate, feed intake, body weight and milk production
 477 variables of dairy ewes under thermo-neutral (TN; n = 8) or heat stress (HS; n = 8) conditions.
 478 Values are least squares means and standard error of the mean (SEM).

Item	TN	HS	SEM	P-value		
				Treatment	Period	T × P ¹
Rectal temperature, °C	38.86	39.63	0.04	0.001	0.007	0.656
Respiratory rate, breaths/min	42	132	2	0.001	0.725	0.367
DM intake, kg/d	2.69	2.39	0.08	0.019	0.001	0.812
Water consumption, L/d	7.14	9.14	0.31	0.001	0.003	0.159
BW change, kg/21d	4.50	-0.38	0.41	0.002	0.226	0.729
Milk yield, kg/d	1.65	1.83	0.15	0.434	0.352	0.883
Fat-corrected milk ² , kg/d	1.64	1.64	0.08	0.985	0.337	0.772
Energy balance ³ , UFL/d	0.45	-0.03	0.09	0.003	0.005	0.886
Milk composition						
Fat, %	6.81	5.74	0.13	0.001	0.980	0.180
Protein, %	6.37	5.51	0.13	0.001	0.177	0.049
Lactose, %	4.43	4.74	0.09	0.028	0.427	0.184
Fat : protein ratio	1.07	1.05	0.03	0.539	0.643	0.274
SCC, log ₁₀ /mL	4.40	4.63	0.08	0.066	0.125	0.679
Fat yield, g/d	108	101	4.0	0.305	0.219	0.933
Protein yield, g/d	97.7	94.7	5.2	0.680	0.216	0.812
Lactose yield, g/d	69.4	81.9	7.3	0.250	0.292	0.548
Milk osmolality, mOsm/kg	298	302	1	0.001	0.084	0.008

479 ¹Interaction of treatment (T) × period (P).

480 ²FCM_{6.5%} = kg of milk yield × (0.37 + 0.09 × fat%) according to Pulina et al. (2005).

481 ³Energy balance = Energy intake – [0.0345 × BW^{0.75}] + [0.686 × milk yield, L × (0.0071 × fat, g/L +
 482 0.0043 × protein, g/L + 0.2224)] according to INRA (2018).

483 **Table 3.** Blood metabolites of dairy ewes under thermo-neutral (TN; n = 8) or heat stress (HS; n
 484 = 8) conditions. Values are least squares means and standard error of the mean (SEM).

Item	TN	HS	SEM	P-value		
				Treatment	Period	T × P ¹
Acid-base balance						
Na, mmol/L	146.4	145.9	0.3	0.264	0.018	0.772
K, mmol/L	4.28	4.41	0.06	0.154	0.610	0.619
Ca, mmol/L	1.31	1.33	0.01	0.224	0.650	0.001
Cl, mmol/L	105.8	107.1	0.5	0.098	0.613	0.693
Total CO ₂ , mmHg	26.3	24.3	0.6	0.023	0.362	0.687
Anion Gap, mmol/L	19.6	19.9	0.4	0.564	0.088	0.629
Energy metabolism						
Glucose, g/dL	60.7	58.7	1.8	0.488	0.798	0.774
Non esterified fatty acids, mmol/L	0.13	0.13	0.02	0.869	0.057	0.444
β-hydroxybutyrate, mmol/L	0.45	0.44	0.04	0.909	0.820	0.157
Cholesterol, mg/dL	107	99	10	0.556	0.981	0.176
Hematocrit, % PCV	22.1	20.8	0.6	0.130	0.179	0.240
Hemoglobin, mmol/L	7.5	7.1	0.2	0.134	0.193	0.226
Protein metabolism						
Creatinine, mg/dL	0.59	0.81	0.02	0.001	0.988	0.099
Blood urea N, mg/dL	20.8	21.6	0.51	0.245	0.172	0.006
Albumin, g/dL	3.4	3.4	0.1	0.480	0.020	0.450

485 ¹Interaction of treatment (T) × period (P).

486 **Table 4.** Metabolite kinetics in response to glucose tolerance test, insulin tolerance test, and
 487 epinephrine challenge in dairy ewes under thermo-neutral (TN; n = 4) or heat stress (HS; n = 4).
 488 Values are least squares means and standard error of the mean (SEM).

Item	TN	HS	SEM	P-value
Glucose tolerance test				
Glucose				
Basal, mg/dL	62.7	59.6	1.6	0.186
Peak, mg/dL	94	245	28	0.028
CR ₆₀ ¹ , %/min	1.7	2.9	0.2	0.010
AUC _{45 min} ² , mg/L × min	1258	2333	318	0.071
AUC _{90 min} , mg/L × min	1321	2457	375	0.093
GLU-t _{1/2} ³ , min	41.7	25.1	2.45	0.004
Insulin				
Basal, µg/L	0.44	0.51	0.08	0.562
Peak, µg/L	2.92	3.58	1.11	0.433
CR ₆₀ ¹ , %/min	3.1	3.6	0.79	0.664
AUC _{45 min} , µg /L × min	32.7	44.4	18.3	0.258
AUC _{90 min} , µg /L × min	35.4	46.5	5.8	0.245
Insulin tolerance test				
Glucose				
Basal, mg/dL	59.2	59.4	1.8	0.934
Nadir, mg/dL	31.7	34.0	2.5	0.542
AUC _{120 min} , mg/dL × min	-522	-386	87	0.313
ISBGR ⁴ , %	0.47	0.40	0.04	0.258
Non-esterified fatty acids				
Basal, mmol/L	0.26	0.34	0.05	0.304
Nadir, mmol/L	0.19	0.15	0.05	0.242
AUC _{120 min} ² , mmol/L × min	1.85	-1.54	0.72	0.017
β-hydroxybutyrate				
Basal, mmol/L	0.43	0.44	0.06	0.881
Nadir, mmol/L	0.36	0.42	0.05	0.486
AUC _{120 min} ² , mmol/L × min	0.18	1.88	1.01	0.301
Epinephrine challenge				
Glucose				
Basal, mg/dL	62.9	61.3	1.5	0.478
Peak, mg/dL	114	104	16	0.682
AUC _{120 min} , mg/dL × min	900	881	152	0.933
Non-esterified fatty acids				
Basal, mmol/L	0.27	0.28	0.04	0.920
Peak, mmol/L	0.44	0.39	0.12	0.578
AUC _{120 min} , mmol/L × min	1.82	-2.10	0.98	0.030
β-hydroxybutyrate				
Basal, mmol/L	0.47	0.46	0.06	0.925
Peak, mmol/L	0.49	0.57	0.13	0.441
AUC _{120 min} , mmol/L × min	-1.17	1.42	0.71	0.047

- 489 ¹Clearance rate form the peak to 60 min = $\frac{\ln(\text{glucose at 5 min}) - \ln(\text{glucose at 60 min})}{\text{min } 60 - \text{min } 5} \times 100$
- 490 ² Area under the curve corrected for the basal levels.
- 491 ³ Glucose half life = $\frac{0.693}{\text{glucose clearance rate}} \times 100$
- 492 ⁴ Insulin stimulated blood glucose response = $\frac{\text{glucose at 0 min} - \text{glucose at 30 min}}{\text{glucose at 0 min}} \times 100$

493 **Figure legend:**

494 **Figure 1.** Plasma glucose (**A**) and insulin (**B**) response to glucose tolerance test of Lacaune dairy
495 ewes under thermo-neutral (TN; ●) or heat stress (HS; ■) conditions. Values are least square
496 means with SEM indicated by vertical bars. * indicates a difference at $P < 0.05$ between TN and
497 HS treatments.

498 **Figure 2.** Plasma glucose response to insulin tolerance test of Lacaune dairy ewes under thermo-
499 neutral (TN; ●) or heat stress (HS; ■) conditions. Values are means with SE indicated by vertical
500 bars. * indicates a difference at $P < 0.05$ between TN and HS treatments.

501 **Figure 3.** Plasma glucose (**A**), NEFA (**B**) and BHBA (**C**) response to epinephrine challenge of
502 Lacaune dairy ewes under thermo-neutral (TN; ●) or heat stress (HS; ■) conditions. Values are
503 least square means with SE indicated by vertical bars. * indicates a difference at $P < 0.05$
504 between TN and HS treatments.

505 **Figure 1.**

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509 **Figure 2.**

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